

Sustainable Education through Digital Inclusion: Providing Research Driven Measure of Organizational Developed for Crossing Educational Boundaries and Enhancing Professional Roles

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Abstract

A key element in improving the quality, social impact, and efficiency of educational institutions such as schools and universities is greater support for teachers and school leaders. Teachers play a central role in imparting knowledge and shared values, as well as in supporting students from low socioeconomic backgrounds. Enabling teachers to meet these demanding tasks requires strategic investments in effective school leadership and a teaching profession grounded in excellent initial education, teamwork, and lifelong professional development. Building on the latest findings from socio-anthropological educational studies, the DIGITclue research consortium provides prospective teachers with methods for inclusive teaching and tools for raising awareness of (in)equality along various axes of social difference. Two manuals, application software for training and development, and a website enable teachers to create more sustainable, inclusive learning environments and respond to the specific needs of students.

This research is based on the trans-European project "Digital Inclusion" (DIGITclue). The idea behind DIGITclue is to provide teachers with the skills, knowledge, and tools they need to use ICT-based interactive and e-learning technologies for inclusive teaching. DIGITclue combines the latest research findings on inclusive pedagogy, ICT-based learning tools, and transcultural education to select, develop, and implement software applications for teacher training using a train-the-trainer approach. A central and innovative aspect is to promote the inclusion of learners with special needs, multilingual teachers, or those working in remote and marginalized areas. It is particularly important here to ensure every step of the development and delivery of teaching materials and to support this with appropriate forms of e-learning. The DIGITclue Hub, a comprehensive website available in six languages – English, German, Croatian, Turkish, Romani, and Czech – supports independent use by teachers and is available free of charge as an open educational resource at www.digitclue.net.

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